

EMOTIONAL INTELLECT

Rashidova Zamira Sharofovna

Termiz State University

Student of the Faculty of Social Sciences

Sattorova Mahliyo

Teacher of the Department of psychology

Abstract: *In this article you will get complete information about intelligence. It is the quality of the psyche that consists of the ability to recognize new things through intelligence. It refers to the ability to learn and memorize through situations, experience, understand and apply abstract concepts, and use one's knowledge to manage the human environment.*

Key words: *Intellect, mind, perception, crystallized intelligence, psychogenetic research, classical logic, non-classical logic, mental retardation,*

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Intellect (Latin intellectus means "perception"; "understanding", "comprehension"; "concept", "reason"). The use of special tests to assess intelligence began in the late 19th and early 20th centuries. The initial task was to assess the level of development of children in order to determine further education programs at school, taking into account individual characteristics. As a measure of the development of intelligence, it was proposed to consider the ratio of the child's actual chronological age and his "mental age". Mental age is determined by performing tasks that children of a certain age can usually solve. The difference between mental and chronological age was considered an indicator of mental retardation (mental age below chronological age) or mental ability (mental age above chronological age). At the same time, the intelligence quotient was proposed: $(\text{mental age} / \text{chronological age}) \times 100\%$.

The necessary conditions of intelligence are the main mental processes that determine the overall success of intellectual activity: attention, memory, thinking, speech, speed of mental processes, etc. 'is the result of mysteries; It is evaluated by tests for vocabulary, reading, calculation, taking into account social norms, etc. more descriptive intelligence than 'lim. A series is evaluated with tests to identify patterns in numbers and figures, spatial operations, etc. Culture-independent intelligence tests have been developed to assess free intelligence (eg, Cattell's Culture-Independent Intelligence Test, Raven's Standard At the same time, different authors distinguish different basic "factors of mind" from one or two to 120. The division of the mind into many components prevents the understanding of its totality. Home psychology is based on the principle of the unity of the intellect, its relationship with the individual. Much attention is paid to the study of the interrelationship of practical and theoretical intelligence, their dependence on the emotional and volitional characteristics of a person. The inconsistency of statements about the innate conditionality of differences in the level of intellectual development between representatives of different nationalities and social groups was shown. At the same time, it is recognized that the intellectual abilities of a person depend on the socio-

economic conditions of life. The specific definition of intelligence and the characteristics of its measurement tools depend on the nature of the corresponding socially significant activities of the individual's field (education, production, politics, etc.).

As the intellect is formed, its normal pathology is also observed. The pathology of the mind (dementia) can be congenital or acquired. Congenital dementia: mental retardation is a congenital or acquired significant impairment of mental abilities in early childhood (up to 3 years old). mental retardation can be caused by various etiological and pathogenetic factors affecting fetal development, birth or the first years of life. " was the term (Greek oligos - small, phren - mind, i.e. dementia), but in modern classifications of mental illness it has been replaced with the term "mental retardation". Acquired dementia: dementia (lat. de - without + mens - from the mind) is a permanent, irreversible loss of previously formed intelligence due to various brain diseases. It is manifested by the loss of previously formed intellectual and practical skills, knowledge, a decrease in the general productivity of mental activity, and a change in personality. Mental retardation is not a painful process, but a pathological condition, the result of a harmful effect that once acted and does not tend to develop. Previously, there were three levels of mental retardation:

1. Idiocy (Greek - idiotea, ignorance).
2. Imbecility (from Latin - im - without + baculus - rod, staff, that is, inability to do without intellectual help).
3. Debilitate (lat. - debilis - disabled, weak, weak).

In the 10th revision of the International Classification of Diseases (1994), mental retardation is divided into four levels of severity: mild, moderate, severe and profound (that is, immobility is divided into two levels - moderate and severe mental development).

1. Idiocy is the most gross violation of the development of cognitive abilities. People with severe mental retardation cannot master even the most basic self-care skills (dressing, washing, using cutlery, etc.), their speech is either not formed at all or with little consists of a number of simple words that they understand. They have little speech, may not recognize the people they care for (eg, mother), do not distinguish edible from inedible (swallows inedible), often do not have an idea about spatial relations (for example, about height: they fall from a great height), rarely form ideas about hot, bitter, etc. (can be injured, burned). In most cases, underdeveloped intelligence is accompanied by motor disorders and severe somatic anomalies. The lives of such patients, who need constant care and supervision of others, are defined by the satisfaction of the most basic life needs. People with severe mental retardation have an IQ below 20.

2. Severe mental retardation (severe variants of imbecility) Cognitive activity is limited to the ability to form only the simplest imaginations; abstract thinking, generalization does not exist. Patients learn only basic self-care skills that cannot be taught. Vocabulary is limited to one or two dozen words, enough to meet their basic needs. Often there are neurological diseases. Patients need constant attention and care. The IQ of these patients is in the range of 20-34.

3. Moderate mental retardation (lighter variants of imbecility) People with moderate mental retardation are able to form more and more complex representations than people with severe mental retardation. They acquire the skills of self-service, they can master the simplest labor

operations by teaching imitation movements. Their vocabulary is richer, they can express themselves with simple phrases, carry on a simple conversation. The relative adaptation of these individuals is possible only in conditions that are well known to them, any change in the situation will lead them to generalizations that allow them to transfer existing ideas from specific (directly experienced) ideas. can be difficult due to the impossibility of passing. experience in new situations. Such people cannot live independently, they need constant guidance and supervision. Some of them do the simplest work in specially created conditions (for example, in medical and labor workshops). The IQ of these patients is in the range of 35-49.

4. Mild level of mental retardation (deficiency) In these cases, cognitive disorders are difficulty in forming complex concepts and generalizations, impossibility or difficulty of abstract thinking. Thinking is mainly visual-figurative, everyday speech is often well developed (sometimes complex abstract concepts are used in it, but their meaning is not always well understood). In most cases, people with mild mental retardation can successfully perform daily household chores and show good practical awareness ("their abilities exceed their knowledge" - E. Kraepelin).

Conclusion: Intelligence is the most complex psychophysiological process of a person. The level of IQ is directly related to this form of intelligence. It is precisely this level of intelligence that begins to form under the influence of the complex activity of our mind. becomes more appropriate and the intellect becomes more complex.

List of used literature:

1. Патология интеллекта <https://psychiatr.ru/education/slide/365/https://>
2. postnauka.ru/longreads/86864 Генетика и интеллекта
3. Эмоциональный интеллект. Развитие базовых эмоций: рабочая тетрадь. (Трясорукова Т)
4. Психика и жизнь (Бехтеров)
5. <http://ebook.tsue.uz/public/ebooks/>